

PROTEOLYTIC ACTIVITY OF BLOOD PLASMA IN PATIENTS WITH ANGINA PECTORIS**Polianska O.,***Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine***Tashchuk V.,***Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine***Hulaha O.,***Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine***Moskaliuk I.,***Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine***Olinchuk V.***Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10650534>**Abstract**

We examined 82 patients with angina pectoris of II and III functional classes. It was found that with an increase in the functional class of angina, the lysis of high-molecular-weight proteins increases, and the prevalence of painless episodes of myocardial ischemia is accompanied by an increase in the lysis of low-molecular-weight peptides and the degradation of azocoll.

Keywords: proteolytic system, angina pectoris.

Introduction. Blood plasma has several complex systems that participate in the body's protective and regulatory reactions. The main proteolytic systems of blood include the clotting, kinin, renin-angiotensin system, fibrinolysis, and the complement system. Limited proteolysis reactions play an important role in achieving a rapid generalized response to a stressor, contributing to the realization of the body's stress response and may lead to a decrease in the contractile ability of the myocardium. The activity of the limited proteolysis reactions plays a crucial role even in the early stages of coronary risk development. These changes may be primary in the chain of metabolic disorders and the formation of corresponding stress response, manifested by an increase in proteolytic activity at the early stages of coronary atherosclerosis and its exhaustion with high coronary risk. Proteolytic enzymes participate in various physiological processes. Reaction of unlimited proteolysis of peptide bonds in inactive precursor proteins are of particular importance, leading to the formation of active forms of enzymes, hormones, and peptides. As a result of unlimited proteolysis processes from proopiomelanocortin, a series of biologically active peptides are formed: endorphins, corticotropin, melanotropins, the secretion of which increases during stress states. Proteolytic enzymes with high biological activity pose a potential danger to most protein structures of tissues. Proteolysis control proteins have also been found in the brain – proteolysis inhibitors. The secretion and inactivation of neuropeptides play an important role in the implementation of the molecular mechanisms of pain syndrome. In response to pain, the hypothalamus releases adrenocorticotrophic-releasing factor into the pituitary, leading to the formation of endorphins, which act on various tissue receptors and lead to a reduction in pain sensation [1].

The aim of the study. To study the proteolytic activity of blood plasma in patients with various forms of angina pectoris, focusing on the lysis of azoalbumin, azocasein, and azocoll.

Materials and Methods. A total 82 patients with angina pectoris of II (CII) and III (CIII) functional classes (FC) were examined, with the determination of plasma proteolytic activity. Azoalbumin (lysis of low-molecular-weight proteins), azocasein (lysis of high-molecular-weight proteins), and azocoll (collagen lysis) (Simko Ltd., Lviv) were used for the analysis. Holter monitoring of electrocardiograms was performed on all patients. Among the examined patients, 40 had predominantly painful episodes (PMI), and 42 had painless episodes of myocardial ischemia (PPMI). The average age of the patients was 53.2 years. Mathematical analysis of the obtained results was carried out on an IBM PC 386 computer using the "Fox Pro" and "DBase" databases, calculating mean values, standard deviations, and the Student's t-test.

Research results and their discussion. The analysis of proteolytic activity of blood plasma in patients with different functional classes of angina revealed (Table 1) that the degradation of low-molecular-weight proteins did not differ in the comparison groups. The degradation of high-molecular-weight proteins in patients with angina pectoris increased directly proportional to the increase in FC of angina. For example, azocasein lysis in patients with CIII increased by 30.16% compared to CII. Collagen degradation also tended to increase with the increase in angina FC, but these changes were statistically insignificant.

It is known that lysosomes and lysosomal enzymes play an important role in the changes in the ultrastructure of the myocardium during hypoxia, stress, including emotional-painful stress, leading to membrane destabilization and the transition of enzymes into the cell cytoplasm. The activation of lysosomes is primarily associated with neurohormonal regulatory influences, among which catecholamines, glucagon, activating lysosomes through the adenylate cyclase system, the generation of cAMP, and the stimulation of cAMP-dependent protein kinase are of great importance. Lately, significant emphasis has been placed on the activation of

lysosomes through lipid hydroperoxides, the content of which in the myocardium increases during hypoxia. In stressful myocardial damage, the release of proteases from lysosomes with a disturbance of calcium transfer from the cytoplasm to the sarcoplasmic reticulum, focal contraction of myofibril areas, and their lysing by proteases are of particular importance [1]. However, under conditions of energy deficit, the weakening of cAMP-dependent lysosomal reactions to regulatory neurohormonal influences during stress is possible. Hypoxia and energy deficit lead to the activation of anaerobic glycolysis and acidosis, which destabilizes lysosome membranes (2). This type of reaction is proven to have a cardioprotective effect.

To assess proteolysis in patients with different clinical manifestations of myocardial ischemia, we compared the activity of these indicators in patients with PPMI and PMI. It was found that the destruction of low-molecular-weight peptides in PPMI was almost 2 times higher than in PMI. No differences between the groups were found in the degradation of high-molecular-weight proteins. The lysis of azocoll was likely higher in PPMI.

This fact may indicate the significant role of proteolysis in the realization of pain sensations during myocardial ischemia. It is known that one of the pathogenetic chains of stress-induced heart damage is the disruption of lysosomal membrane integrity, leading to the release of proteolytic enzymes from lysosomes. Together with the effects of the lipid triad, this can result in damage to sarcolemma membranes, leading to changes in pain perception.

The proven important role of tissue proteases in providing unlimited proteolysis of various proteins leads to the formation of biologically active compounds such as enzymes, hormones, and neuropeptides. The introduction of bradykinin causes severe pain, and the transformation of kininogen into bradykinin occurs under the action of the proteolytic enzyme- plasma kallikrein. Bradykinin is one of significant mediators investigated for its role in facilitating cardioprotection and neuroprotection through different types of ischemic conditioning, such as preconditioning, postconditioning and remote ischemic preconditioning [1]. Thus, unlimited proteolysis processes have a protective nature, and the formation of opioid hormones has an anti-stress direction and increases the sensitivity threshold. However, the formation of kinins with significant proteolytic activity in plasma and tissues leads to the appearance of pain syndrome through irritation of pain receptors.

It is known that through proteolytic cleavage of high-molecular-weight proteins, preproendothelin is transformed into endothelin, the vasoconstrictor effect of which exceeds that of angiotensin II, serotonin, and norepinephrine by 10-100 times. An increase in its

plasma level is detected at the onset of atherosclerosis and myocardial ischemia.

Obviously, in the mechanisms of myocardial damage, not a single but several mechanisms of lysosome changes in cardiomyocytes exist. However, they are not activated simultaneously but in different sequences, which may determine clinical manifestations, the functional state of the myocardium during stress tests, and the presence or absence of pain during myocardial ischemia. Often, the cause of energy deficit in the myocardium is pronounced acidosis of various origins, resulting in a disruption of calcium transport in cardiomyocytes [2].

The identified changes in proteolysis in various manifestations of IHD indicate the revealed pathogenetic features of the course of each form. For example, the proteolysis activity in CIII is characterized by significant activation of high-molecular-weight peptide lysis with possible formation of endothelin, which can induce coronary spasm alongside norepinephrine, vasopressin, and serotonin [3].

The severity of the pain syndrome may depend on the activity of high-molecular-weight peptides lysis, and the parallel increase in degradation of low-molecular-weight proteins and azocoll is associated with the occurrence of painless myocardial ischemia.

Thus, the changes in proteolytic activity of blood plasma identified in various forms of IHD require a review of some aspects of patient treatment standardization. They necessitate consideration of the identified features of proteolysis in the selection of pharmacological agents for their targeted correction.

Conclusions. The increase in the functional class of angina is accompanied by an elevation in the lysis of high-molecular-weight proteins. The parallel increase in the lysis of low-molecular-weight peptides and azocoll in angina may contribute to the severity of the pain syndrome.

References:

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Table 1.

Proteolytic activity of blood plasma in patients with different types of angina pectoris

N	Groups	Lysis of azoalbumin E 440.ml- 1.hr-1	Lysis of azocasein E 440.-1.hr- 1	Lysis of azocoll E 440.-1.hr-1
1	CII n=48	7,03 ± 0,52	9,58 ± 0,77	0,61 ± 0,06
2	CIII n=34	7,63 ± 0,67	12,47 ± 0,94 P1-2***	0,63 ± 0,04
3	PMI n=42	7,32 ± 0,85	14,82 ± 1,08	0,84 ± 0,07
4	PPMI n=40	12,43 ± 0,89 P3,4***	14,34 ± 0,98	1,04 ± 0,08 P3,4*

Note: *- probability coefficient P between the specified groups < 0,05;** <0,01;*** <0,001 (only statistically significant differences are provided)